

Birgit Nilsson

Färlöv, Sweden December 2000

My dear John,

First of all I want to wish you a very happy Birthday, and many many happy returns, filled with wonderful music and excellent health!

Secondly: I want to welcome you in the "Grown up's Club!"

When I had the great pleasure working with you, I was always amazed that somebody as young as you were so advanced and such an excellent accompanist. Later on I found out, that you were not that young as you looked;..

Even though I have not seen you for some years, I bet, that you are still that tall and slender young- looking man, without a single grey hair on your lovely head.

John my Dear, those wonderful years when we made music together were the highlight of my career. Do I need to tell you, that you had a big part in it? You were also a great travelling- companion, who, like my self never made life more complicated than it had to be. We had many good laughs, but also a few not so good ones-.

Do you remember after a concert in Lincoln, Nebraska, when it took us 20 hour's by planes and a rented car in snow storm's (in the North) and thunder storm's(in the South) before we could reach our destination so the next concert could start in time. That night I almost emptied my whole repertoire of funny jokes, which I had to tell you to keep you awake whilst you were driving. I am sure you agree that it was not our best concert, ever..

I close with a big BIRTHDAY-KISS and loads of good wishes. I am sure you will still help and inspire many young singers into STARDOM!
How I envy them !!!

Yours

Birgit